

Religious Education in Indonesia

Grassroots Perspectives

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Preface

The nearly 40 key words listed above the contributions in this volume on *Religious Education in Indonesia* revolve around four themes: religion, education, trauma, and a multifaith society. The articles explore these themes in relation to the recent past, present, and future of the Republic of Indonesia as a plural society with conflicts and encounters between religions and to the crucial role education plays in it.

Its seven authors are young Indonesian PhD candidates supervised by the Graduate School of the Faculty of Religion and Theology of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. The Graduate School organized a small-scale international conference for these PhD candidates that took place on 23 March 2022. In this partly online meeting in Amsterdam, they presented part of their PhD research to each other, to other Indonesian PhD students from outside the Vrije Universiteit, to their supervisors, and other interested parties. This volume contains these presentations and makes them available to a wider circle of interested parties. The result provides relevant grassroots insight into the topicality of a society that is in transformation and facing challenges, including those in religious education.

For the participating PhD students, the conference proved useful not only academically in terms of preparing, presenting, discussing, and editing an academic paper, but it was also inspiring in terms of content. New questions and new perspectives arose, and coherences and connections were discovered. Above all, the meeting proved to be a welcome encouragement to continue with PhD research and writing.

Thanks go to Risvan, Lydia, Christofer, Liliya, Nelson, Leonardo, Karmelia, and their supervisors, to Dr. Henry Jansen for his careful linguistic correction of the contributions, and to the Faculty Board for funding this production. I had the pleasure of functioning for some time as general supervisor, and with the publication of this volume as an interim snapshot, I bid them farewell. I do so with grateful memories and full of expectations about the contribution these representatives of a new generation of young researchers will still make to academia and society.

Wim Janse, Professor Emeritus of Religion and Public Policy
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, February 2023

A Congruent Approach: A Contribution to the Debate about Religion, Belief and/or¹ Non-Religion in Indonesia

Risvan Latupeirissa

Abstract

This paper examines historical issues before arriving at its proposed congruent approach. Historical studies are also deliberately used to understand the Indonesian context and map out the approaches that can be offered to address local needs. This paper tackles three major questions: 1) How are the terms religion, belief, and/or non-religion currently used in Indonesia? 2) What are the main characteristics that emerge from the concept of religion that prevails in Indonesia today? 3) How does the offer of a congruent approach contribute to the debate on the discriminatory situation that arises from the terms religion, belief, and/or non-religion? This paper also presents five central ideas behind the history of the concept of religion in Indonesia and five working principles of a 'congruent approach' in reconstructing the understanding concerning the concept of religion. The literature study will be used as a data collection method and historical studies as a data analysis method.

Keywords

congruent approach, religion, belief, non-religion

ORIGIN OF THE CONCEPT OF RELIGION, BELIEF, AND/OR NON-RELIGION IN INDONESIA

Understanding religious life in Indonesia should not start with defining what religion is in the Indonesian context but with how the background of the concept of religion is present and enforced in Indonesia. In what follows, I will describe some aspects of history that eventually gave rise to the understanding of religion in Indonesia as it is today.

Fundamental Points for Understanding the Concept of Religion in Dutch East Indies Policy

Our understanding of religion in Indonesia, which became independent on 17 August 1945, is inseparable from the phenomenon of the Dutch domination of the archipelago for about 350 years before the leaders of each region finally decided to unite in an independent state called Indonesia. As the ruling power before Indonesian independence, the Dutch colonial government regulated the system for the colonies, including its

¹ The term 'belief' is often equated with non-religion in Indonesia.

policies. For Auliya Ridwan, the politics of ‘Dutchification’ had to appear in every layer of society (2016, 228).

Harmen Westra² intended to explain the constitutional law of the Dutch East Indies to students in the Dutch East Indies. Especially in his *De Technische Hoogeschool te Bandoeng*, he attempted to write a short, intelligible, and comprehensive description of the Dutch government regulatory system for the Dutch East Indies. He began by writing down the main motivations for the regulatory process as illustrated in the following quote:

De vestiging van het nederlandsch gezag is niet het gevolg geweest van een bepaalden opzet als zoodanig, doch de onontkoombare noodwendigheid haar octrooi te handhaven en haar handelsbelangen en stapelplaatsen te beveiligen, dwong de Vereenigde Oost-Indische-Compagnie ertoe een koloniaal rijk te stichten. Rust ons gezag derhalve goeddeels op daadwerkelijke vestiging, geconsolideerd is het door verdragen met inlandsche vorsten zoolang deze nog soeverein waren en politieke contracten (lange contracten en korte verklaringen) na hunne suzeriniteit, zoomede door verdragen met vreemde mogendheden. (Westra 1927, 1)

[Translation: The establishment of Dutch authority was not the result of any particular purpose as such, but the inevitable need to defend its patent and to secure its commercial interests and warehouses compelled the Dutch East India Company to establish a colonial empire. Our authority, therefore, rests principally on actual establishment; treaties with native princes solidified it when they were still sovereign, as did political contracts (long contracts and short declarations) after their suzerainty was shifted, as well as by treaties with foreign powers.]

The establishment of Dutch authority was not the result of any particular purpose as such, but the inevitable need to defend its patent and to secure its commercial interests and warehouses compelled the Dutch East India Company to establish a colonial empire. Our authority, therefore, rests principally on actual establishment; treaties with native princes solidified it when they were still sovereign, as did political contracts (long contracts and short declarations) after their suzerainty was shifted, as well as by treaties with foreign powers. (Westra 1927, 1)

In general, Westra’s writings reveal the organisation of foreign relations and domestic affairs, including religion, in the colonies. But he provided a clear framework from the very beginning for making the policies formed

² According to the *Catalogus Professorum Academiae Rheno-Traiectinae, Universiteit Utrecht*, Harmen Westra was appointed Professor of Constitutional Law for the Dutch East Indies and *adat* law on 12 October 1931 until 1942. He was also chair of the Fund for Indological Studies (from 12 October 1931 until 11 June 1942) which was controlled by the Department of Indology.

<https://profs.library.uu.nl/index.php/profrec/getprofdata/2350/2/2/0%20access> March 11, 2022.

at that time into a blueprint designed to protect commercial interests and warehouses³ so that a colonial empire could be established. In this case, economic reasons were rooted in colonial policies.⁴ Other sources affirm that the most important innovations in the Dutch East Indies were those related to the economy; even organisational and managerial developments were designed to facilitate the work that supported the envisioned economic system.⁵

While the above-mentioned works examine the economic interests behind the Dutch colonial policies, Turenhout analyses them in three respects (2021, 19-26). He compares current Dutch policy to the policy during the Dutch colonial period, and this comparison is linked by three patterns: attempts at social/cultural, economic, and political control. There were three aspects to social/cultural control. First, the Dutch controlled education and imposed their expertise (implementing Western educational standards or educational programmes⁶ in the colonies to enforce

³ Doel writes that 823 million guilders flowed into the Dutch treasury from the Dutch East Indies between 1831 and 1877 (about 50 years out of a total of nearly 350 years of Dutch domination). For him, this resulted in relatively low taxes in the Netherlands at that time (1831-1877), which reduced the tax burden and delayed the implementation of the modern taxation system, including income tax until the end of the nineteenth century. Even the tax on basic needs could be abolished. He added that the money was also used to pay off the state debt and the debts of the Dutch East Indies and finance all kinds of public works, including the construction of the railway network in the Netherlands (Doel 2010, 187).

⁴ We need to look at any individual case from many sides. This also applies to the issue of colonialism in the Dutch East Indies. Doel's writings help us see that, despite the poverty in the Dutch East Indies as a result of colonialism, Dutch domination still led to growth in several fields: stimulating local industry, prosperity for certain groups in Java (although shared poverty for others); improving infrastructure and transportation routes; designing education courses for some people who were deliberately sent abroad to return as employees – all these constituted the other face of colonialism (see Doel 2010, 179-208). Thee Kian Wie added that the Dutch government also built elementary and secondary schools as well as various higher educational institutions, including the Technical School (*Technische Hogeschool* – TH) in Bandung, the Medical School (*Geneeskundige Hogeschool*- GH), the Law School (*Rechtshogeschool*- RH) in Jakarta, and the School of Agriculture (*Landbouwhogeschool*) in Bogor (Frankema and Buelens 2013, 56). Postcolonial critics see this Dutch government action as done purely for political and economic reasons. Nonetheless, development did occur.

⁵ See Frederick, Worden, and Library of Congress, 1993, 20.

⁶ Regarding education, Quijano reminds us that colonialism affected the production and reproduction of knowledge by imposing an imagined Western culture on non-Western societies (Quijano in Garzón López 2016, 279; Guzmán 2019, 65; Quijano 2000, 540). Mignolo added that the colonial world he imagined was full of 'theo-logical' and 'ego-logical' politics of knowledge and understanding (2007, 459). Continuing the thought of Darcy Ribeiro, Enrique Dussel and Orlando Fals Borda, Robert Richard and Rolena Adorna, Mignolo agrees that the idea of knowledge has also been colonised (Mignolo 2007, 502, 450). Therefore, the task ahead is to decolonise knowledge (Quijano in

modernisation). Second, they held to the assumption that what the southern partners⁷ needed was modernisation.⁸ Third, they exercised control over language (but this model is more common in neo-colonialism).

Mignolo 2007, 451) which he referred to as the ‘delinking process’ (Mignolo 2007, 453, 455 and 459). To emphasise this point, Quijano states that the rediscovery of the past is not meant to recover nostalgia (or lost innocence) but to integrate wisdom by unifying the tree of knowledge and the tree of life, so it could become the basis for alternative rationalities against the instrumental rationalism that dominates our present (Quijano 1993, 150).

⁷ Turenhout states that the mapping of southern and northern partners on a world map, in which the North is considered a better world model by Northerners (2021, 20), was proposed by Alex Martins (see Martins 2020, 135-153). The world map itself has long been criticised for legitimising the idea of Eurocentrism (Villanueva and Gonzalo 2000, 61-66). Turenhout disagreed with the term ‘Southern’ as too geographical when discussing countries subjected to colonialism. Though it is located in the South, Australia cannot be seen as part of the South. He could not, however, find a more appropriate term to use so he chose the terms ‘South and North’ in his article (2021, 20).

⁸ Cf. here Martins, who says that humans are inclined to move in a linear path from a traditional to a modern society, following the standards set by the global North (Martins 2020, 140; Turenhout 2021, 19). In my view, modernisation, which was considered a necessity for European society at that time, ultimately justified colonialism. Mignolo says that the dark side of modernity up until now is ‘continuous colonial reproduction’ (2007, 450). Kaunda and Hewitt argue that colonialism is a constitutive dimension of modernity and that there is no modernity without colonialism (2015, 381). Knowledge and understanding of modernisation encourage the emergence of a feeling of superiority from European groups over other groups that are considered unfamiliar and even far from the framework of modernity. This feeling of superiority made European societies that carry modernity to other community all around the world position themselves as a point of reference, which later became known as the ‘Eurocentric perspective’. Scholars state that colonialism is a process of the hegemonic representation and expansion of the Eurocentric understanding related to the position of Europe as the centre and the domination of others as a necessary dimension of modernity (Escobar 2004, 217; Kaunda and Hewitt 2015, 381). In the Australian context, some think that a group of Aboriginal people called ‘full blood’ would eventually die out because of their inferiority (Cunneen 2005, 64). For Europeans at that time, inferior races were only capable of producing inferior cultures (Guzmán 2019, 63). In another context, Africans were allocated to the bottom rung on a metaphorical ladder of human development (Hodge 1971, 92; Kaunda and Hewitt 2015, 379, 384). In Asia, Atkinson reports that, with Calvinism and Eurocentrism, the Dutch fostered a sense of Indonesian ‘backwardness’ that continued to be applied by certain groups in the country to minority groups in Indonesia after the Dutch left (Atkinson 1987, 687). Quijano states that, in the expansion of European colonial domination over the world, the Indian-American community, along with the so-called ‘black Africans’, belonged to the same group: ‘primitives’ (Quijano 2000, 542; Guzmán 2019, 63). While other writers used the term ‘barbarian’ (Kaunda and Hewitt 2015, 381; Dallmayr 1989, 222-223), Gomez chose three words to represent the non-European world for Europeans at that time: ‘uncivilised,’ showing evidence of ‘ignorance’, and ‘backwardness’. As a result, they had no room in European

According to Turenhout (2021, 19-26), four things apply to the governance of the economy. First, institutions and regulations – parameters and rules – were imposed (to take control of an area). Second, the people were segregated by the economy (Western education was given to the upper and middle classes but at the same time the lower classes were put to work in the agricultural sector for export needs in projects like the *cultuurstelsel* one,⁹ which was reinforced by labour policies.¹⁰ Third, conditional exchanges or ‘economic agreements’ (they run all or part of the trading system) were enforced. Fourth, (neo-)liberal policies were implemented. In liberal economic policies, modernity is seen as the final stage that must be achieved. Therefore, the use of violence is approved as a necessary means to encourage a sense of ‘submission’. At the same time, modern and humanistic educational methods had to be applied immediately to bring the Dutch East Indies into the modern world.¹¹

Turenhout (2021, 19-26) adds that four things apply to political control. First, they enforced racial politics: skin colour is institutionalised in order to assess one’s value as a human being while whites are considered superior.¹² Second, they set up conditional (aid) schemes. They built a dependency relationship between the coloniser and the colony that was controlled by the coloniser, including determining who had the right to work or even attend the school that had just been opened.¹³ Third, they promoted ‘good governance’ (the application of Western governance styles and principles related to the concept of ‘good governance’, e.g., effectiveness and transparency). Fourth, they enforced partnerships led by the North.

civilisation, and the mission of ‘civilising’ others for ‘rescue’ was something that had to be done (Gómez Isa 2018, 173). Gomez’s opinion was rooted in aspirations embodied in the two international laws of the time: the General Act of the Berlin Conference on West Africa (1884-1885: Berlin 1892, 4), Article 6, and the Covenant of the League of Nations (League of Nations 1919), Article 22. These rules legitimated actions against groups considered to be outside the standards set by the modern world (Gómez Isa 2018, 173). On this basis, colonial laws and policies that targeted backwardness (Cunneen 2005, 60; Guzmán 2019, 64), including the destruction of pre-existing legal and social systems (Guzmán 2019, 64) were considered ‘reasonable’. I agree with Kaunda and Hewitt’s warning that the ‘rescue’ act that Europeans had in mind would actually be seen by non-Europeans as de-civilisation and hatred for what they have (2015, 384).

⁹ Cf. Auliya Ridwan 2016, 244, 229.

¹⁰ See Turenhout 2021, 22.

¹¹ The following quote is a very clear example: ‘These people (the Ogadens) must learn submission by the bullets- It’s the only school. After that you may begin more modern and humane methods of education’. See Kiwanuka 1970, 296.

¹² Cf. Staples 1976, 39-42; Quijano 2000, 534-535.

¹³ Cf. Cribb 1993, 225-245, and Suratminto 2013, 78-80.

These three characteristics (social/cultural control, economy and politics) seemed to play a significant role in the birth of policies in the Dutch East Indies. If the main content behind these three characteristics is examined in detail, however, it can be reduced to two main elements: 1) the mass implementation of the idea of modernity by imposing Western standards and 2) economics (capitalism). Lindblad states that, in the Indonesian context, the Dutch government at that time – which Frankema and Buelens called an ‘enlightened government’ (Frankema and Buelens 2013, 245) – was demonstrating an attempt to present modernity with the clear face of capitalism in a traditional context (Lindblad 2013, 212-7, 224).

It can be concluded that two essential ideas were associated with the policies that prevailed in the Dutch East Indies. The first is the notion of modernity, which is ‘an obligation’ for the colonisers to enlighten the colonised by having them conform to Western norms. Here, education is seen as a path to conformity to Western standards. The religious policies issued at that time must also be viewed in this way. The second point is the importance of capitalism for the colonies. As in the previous point, education policy and religious policy regulations cannot be viewed apart from these interests.

The Polarisation of Islam as a Religion; Islam as a Political Ideology and Tradition (*Adat*): Snouck Hurgronje’s Advice

Religious policy in the Dutch East Indies was related to how the Dutch colonisers reacted to Muslim groups. In this case, everyone needs to recall Snouck Hurgronje’s influence in Indonesia, including the polarisation of Islam as a religion, Islam as a political ideology and as tradition (*adat*). He is credited as being the ‘prime architect’ of the Dutch Islamic policy in the Dutch East Indies (Benda 1967, 1001) with the title and role of Advisor for Native and Arabic Affairs (McFate 2019, 431; Benda 1967, 1001). On the one hand, he was described as ‘the conscience of the Dutch government’ (Benda 1967, 1001) and on the other, he is eschewed and demeaned by many in Indonesia as the Dutch spy who emasculated Islam in Aceh.

Going beyond that debate, I will try to explain some of the reasons that led me to conclude that he was the most realistic person in the tense situation between the ‘colonisers’ and the ‘colonised’ at that time, albeit at an unavoidable cost. These reasons and the conclusion, which we will use later to understand the polarisation that eventually emerged, divide and lead to the unfair treatment of religious people in Indonesia to this day. The

separation of religion and customs in Indonesia cannot be understood without this source.

Snouck Hurgronje is well known because of his placement in Aceh-Sumatra for the purpose understanding the Islamic community there. Aceh is both the name of the community and the name of the region. Several articles report that this community was a source of fear¹⁴ for the Dutch colonisers. Aceh was the last territory in the Dutch East Indies to come under Dutch control, and it was also the first to leave the Dutch administration (Veer 1985, xi). Veer even said that the Dutch never waged a bigger war than the Aceh War (1870-1942) in terms of the duration and number of casualties.¹⁵ This statement shows the difficulty of conquering the Acehnese people mainly because the Muslim power motivated them with the idea of 'rebellng in the name of Allah'.¹⁶

Montgomery McFate said that fear of Islam – which was believed to be a hegemonic and hierarchical religion – led the Dutch colonial government to impose three central policies (McFate 2019, 420). First, the colonial government allied itself with princes and aristocrats on Java and regional chiefs on other islands who did not seem to follow Islamic legal principles fully (usually only in a lukewarm way). The groups that were invited to join were considered enemies of Islamic fanaticism and even tended to become enemies of the people because of the general belief that they served their own interests, rather than those of the people, through their relations with the Dutch. Second, the process of the Christianisation of the majority of the Indonesian population was seen as a way to eliminate the influence of Islam. Third, they restricted pilgrimages by Indonesians to Mecca, arguing that the programme was 'responsible for spreading agitation, unrest and rebellion in Indonesia'.

¹⁴ This was because of their strong ties to the Middle East. For the colonial government, Mecca was believed to be the centre of an international conspiracy that inspired the spirit of anti-colonial movements in the Muslim world (Burhanudin 2015, 27-28). Snouck Hurgronje considers that to be a misunderstanding of Islam that gave rise to what has recently been called 'Islamophobia'. According to him, Islam was considered to be a tightly organised religion, like Roman Catholicism, loyal to foreign caliphs, and it held great sway over the Indonesian rulers and their people, which was reflected in the provisions of Islamic law. The influence of Islam is also thought to have had a hold on the lives of indigenous groups. Given that, the Islamic community was seen as a formidable enemy. Evidence of fear on the part of the Dutch can be drawn from the formation of the alliance policy described above. More proof of this fear is their proposal of the Christian Mission, which turned out to be very slow in developing (and even in areas that had not been subjected to Islamic influence). Cf. Benda 1958, 339; McFate 2019, 419-420.

¹⁵ Cf. Veer 1985, 254.

¹⁶ See McFate 2019, 419 and cf. Kartodirjo 1966, 140-174; Laffan 2003, 88-97.

The constant fear of Muslims in Aceh and some of the above tactics were considered fruitless.¹⁷ Snouck Hurgronje was sent to Aceh to study the context of Islam there. Burhanudin briefly describes Hurgronje in the following sentence:

Snouck Hurgronje held the opposite view to that of the Dutch authorities. For him, they were unworldly scribes and teachers, most of whom desired nothing more than to serve Allah in peace. As a result, suppression was neither wise nor even necessary. Snouck Hurgronje's views on the peaceful nature of Islam did not hinder him from being cautious of the political danger of Muslim fanaticism. (2015, 32)

His proximity to Muslims (studying in Mecca in 1884-1885, his conversion to Islam, his development of strong relations with Muslims, and marriage to a local Muslim noblewoman in Java)¹⁸ seemed to influence Snouck Hurgronje's view of Islam. Benda claimed that Snouck Hurgronje was a person who viewed indigenous peoples, including the Islamic community there, as human beings and not as statistical entities (Benda 1967, 1001), as the colonialists did at that time. For me, it seems premature for someone to claim immediately that Snouck Hurgronje hated Islam and was simply an accomplice of the colonial government. Further evidence worth considering is the depth of meaning Snouck Hurgronje saw in Islam as evidenced in his reports and writings,¹⁹ as well as his courage in encouraging European groups to accept that Christianisation (with the concept of Christian supremacy)²⁰ should not be forced unless Islam (and thus *adat*) was also accepted.²¹

Snouck Hurgronje actually faced a personal dilemma before arriving at this advice. On the one hand, he was confronted with Dutch nationalism, his understanding of colonial interests, and the enlightening impulse of the modernist paradigm. On the other hand, there was his new awareness that was the result of his encounters with the Islamic community, his deepening appreciation of Islamic thought and seeing it as noble,²² eventually opening himself up to accepting it as something comparable to Christianity. We will see that Snouck Hurgronje did not want to choose one horn of the dilemma.

¹⁷ Cf. McFate 2019, 416.

¹⁸ Cf. Snouck Hurgronje 2007; Snouck Hurgronje 1937, 10; McFate 2019, 422, 424.

¹⁹ Cf. Snouck Hurgronje, 1906.

²⁰ He rejected the false hope of a massive conversion from Islam to Christianity. See McFate 2019, 339-341.

²¹ Cf. Burhanudin 2015, 38; Benda 1958, 341; Van Vollenhoven, one of Snouck Hurgronje's students, also called on Europeans to accept this in his book (Holleman 1981).

²² Cf. Benda 1958, 342.

Starting with his study in Mecca, Snouck Hurgronje realised that Islam actually emphasised peace, but he did not deny the political potential of Islamic fanaticism (Benda 1958, 342). In his view, Islam becomes dangerous when it is dominated by political content. Snouck Hurgronje thus decided to dissect Islam, which seemed so much larger and imposing and split it into two different kinds: Islam as a religion and Islam as a political ideology²³ that favours the development of political power in the form of a caliphate.²⁴ The first group deserved freedom, but the second group had to be treated harshly.

This distinction was, for Snouck Hurgronje, necessary for Islam to meet European demands (that it have an appropriate status to be accepted²⁵). In this context, a modernist attitude to enlightenment, which enabled Europeans to feel superior, was behind the decisions at that time.²⁶ Snouck Hurgronje was confident that he was thus not destroying true Islam but only the violence that entered Islam while at the same time defending Dutch nationalism and interests. This, in his view, was where Islam and Europe could meet.

Snouck Hurgronje said that mutual trust in relationships with adherents of other faiths is ‘more favourable’²⁷ to Muslims, especially those living under European rule (Snouck Hurgronje 1985, 391). He did not see much opportunity to establish a caliphate in the Dutch East Indies. At the same time, he did not see any chance to realise Christianity’s dream of being embraced en masse by everyone in the Dutch East Indies. Therefore, the mutual relationship between the Acehnese (who were predominantly Muslim) and the Dutch (who were predominantly Christian) is very important. For him, what hinders their relationship is the radical side of Islam.²⁸ Given this, for Snouck Hurgronje, his splitting of Islam into two

²³ McFate called Snouck Hurgronje the first Western scholar to distinguish between the political and religious aspects of Islam (McFate 2019, 429).

²⁴ Cf. McFate 2019, 429-9; Benda 1958, 342.

²⁵ Snouck Hurgronje, quoted in McFate, believed that the ‘mediaeval mixture of religion and politics’ made Islam incompatible with the Dutch body politic (religion belonged to the private sphere and government was fully secular) (McFate 2019, 436).

²⁶ Obviously, the standard for determining religion had to be based on constructs built outside the Dutch East Indies (derived from a colonial perspective).

²⁷ The phrase ‘more favorable’ here refers to the advantage that, when the Muslims who tended to oppose the Dutch colonialism (which also brought Christianity) could work together with Dutch colonialists, there would not be a great cost and loss of life. The Muslims would even have the freedom to live in Aceh if they were willing to compromise with the Dutch. Exclusivism and radicalism (specially with a view to establishing a caliphate) were believed to be detrimental to the Islamic side, but openness (compromise with the Dutch, to be precise) could produce benefits in the form of guarantees of security and stability.

²⁸ Today’s readers will be more critical and argue that it is unfair if only the Islamic side has to compromise. Regarding justice, today’s critical readers can argue that

forms is considered the most effective in accommodating the interests of the Dutch government and the interests of Muslims (with the exception of politically charged Muslim groups).

At the same time, Snouck Hurgronje made a ‘clear distinction’ between tradition and religion in contrast to the previous tendency to mix the two. He does not exclude tradition, but he does separate it from religion. Tradition and Islam as a religion would thus be protected, and the Dutch would target only politically motivated Islamic groups. Snouck Hurgronje sees tradition²⁹ as part of the local life (in his opinion, different from religion) but it was also a great asset to be preserved (and later modernised).³⁰ He and his student Van Vollenhoven supported the Dutch colonial authorities in strengthening this group, including indigenous leaders.³¹ The great opportunity to push them towards modernity (Burhanudin 2015, 53) actually facilitates control over them and minimises the impact of political content on Muslim groups in society.

Although Snouck Hurgronje seems to be trying to present a ‘win-win solution’ for all parties in the account given above, Maarif sees this clear distinction as a ‘politics of splitting bamboo’ in order to weaken the indigenous community (2018, 14). What is forgotten is that those who hold the two (tradition and Islam) together³² are also required to choose. One consequence that eventually emerged was that religion had to be interpreted according to colonial standards. Another was that indigenous religious practices, which were attached in the ruling at that time to the term *adat* (tradition) so that they could be easily codified and further regulated, slowly drifted (and continue to do so) out of the field of religious themes. This section should close with Benda’s statement that a ‘modern Indonesia’ (then the Dutch East Indies) requires neither an Islamic Indonesia nor an Indonesia governed by *adat* (tradition) but ‘Westernized Indonesia’ (1958, 344).

Snouck Hurgronje’s suggestion above refers to the intersection of the interests of the two parties (the Dutch colonial government and the Islamic

mutual relations occur and have a big impact if it is not only one side that has to make sacrifices: both sides must be willing to make sacrifices to reach a compromise for mutual benefit.

²⁹ Fasseur attributes the expression *hukum adat* or *adat law* (literally ‘customary law’, ‘common law’, or ‘the law in a tradition’) to Snouck Hurgronje, and the latter used it for the first time in his book *De Atjehers* (The Acehnese) published in 1893 (Davidson and Henley 2007, 51). The term ‘tradition’ and its further elaboration was carried out by his student Van Vollenhoven (Avonius and Sadikin 2010, 4).

³⁰ Van Vollenhoven, as quoted in Avonius and Sadiqin, states that those who practise *adat* are actually carrying out practices that lead to what reconciliation entails (2010, 4).

³¹ Cf. Benda 1958, 346.

³² Clifford Geertz calls both (Islam) Abangan (1996, 149).

groups) with the ‘lowest cost’ option. It is clear, however, that this decision victimises indigenous groups at a later stage, although, animated by the spirit of modernisation, Snouck Hurgronje did not initially aim to victimise them.³³ The modern paradigm actually reduces the identity of indigenous groups and places them outside the realm of religion, even below the standard of religiosity that is recognised by the modern world.

A supplementary question is whether the advice given by Snouck Hurgronje does not have economic content. The development of pepper production at that time in Aceh (Graf et al. 2010, 64) and the ‘win-win solution’³⁴ objective offered by Snouck Hurgronje seem to indicate that ‘the protection of the colonial economic interests’ was included in the framework of satisfying both parties. In this case, the political structure and policies issued regarding religion can also be read from this perspective. Furthermore, policies on religion were used to reinforce the prevailing power structure to preserve colonial interests.

The Cosmological System of the Indonesian Indigenous Community before Colonialism

If Snouck Hurgronje is worth remembering when discussing Dutch politics in relation to religion, then Samsul Maarif is a name worth mentioning when discussing indigenous religion in the Indonesian context. Working with various groups of indigenous people whom he calls adherents of ‘ancestral religion’ (literally, indigenous religion), he creates a mental map to understand their paradigm, which he sees as differing from the cosmological system of the world religions paradigm. In his view, in the

³³ Today’s readers are too quick to accuse him of underestimating the indigenous religious perspectives in favor of modernisation. The reasons given by readers today are generally related to issues of human rights, injustice, discrimination, and so on. With the development of the world of knowledge and the struggle for human rights being fought everywhere lately, it will be clearer for today’s reader to map the indigenous religion paradigm and the world religions paradigm and understand the tension between these two paradigms. However, it was not easy to understand these two paradigms during Snouck Hurgronje’s time, especially in the midst of the political tensions between the colonisers and the colonised. In addition, within a limited time, he was given the opportunity to analyse the situation and provide advice before the Dutch government took a decision in producing a new policy related to Islam (to be precise, with regard to religion) in the Dutch East Indies. Regarding how he treated the Muslims in order to minimise losses as much as possible, I predict he would have been more careful in his decisions if he had a chance to understand it from our contemporary perspective.

³⁴As stated earlier, this win-win solution is seen as benefiting both the Dutch colonial power and the Islamic community.

world religions paradigm, which is based on a Western monotheistic ontology, the cosmological system utilises a hierarchical model for categories of beings (divinity, humanity, and nature), (Maarif 2018, 109). In Maarif's view, the three stand in a hierarchical relationship:³⁵ the supernatural/divinity is more powerful than culture/humans, and culture is more powerful than nature.³⁶ Utilising the work of Kenneth Morrison, Maarif said that the characteristic form of this paradigm was a universally applied 'hierarchical cosmology', though it is based on ethnocentricity (Morrison 2005, 25; Picard 2011, 2; Maarif 2018). Timothy Fitzgerald writes:

The discipline of religious studies has been historically constructed around a highly unstable and contested category 'religion'; yet despite the historical struggles over its meaning within Christian history, religion has come to be researched and described as though it is a transparent notion, based on common-sense observable reality, universally applicable, a word and an idea which unproblematically translate into any language of any culture at any time in human history. (Fitzgerald 2007, 4)

Picard describes the world religions paradigm along these lines as follows:

Such a process of 'religionization' resulted in a complex evolution, marked by rationalization the formulation of a canonical corpus, its institutionalization and its effective socialization (Hefner 1993) – as well as by secularization – desacralization of the immanent concrete in favour of an abstract and transcendent divine (Hefner 1998) – along with scripturalization and standardized practices. (Picard 2011, 2)

Awareness of the concept of religion (which is full of Christian theology)³⁷ and Western modernity, which was later standardised as universal)³⁸, prompted Maarif to map the indigenous religion paradigm, which had shifted significantly after the process of colonialism in Indonesia. He argues that the supernatural/divinity as the essential element of religion (today) was appropriated by early Christian theologians (Maarif 2018,

³⁵ In all cultures, humans are placed below divinity. In this context, 'worship' is understood as the type of relationship that must be formed between humans and the more powerful supernatural (divine) entity above them. Nature is below culture/humans, which means that it is seen as object as opposed to subject. In this context, the relationship pattern between humans/culture and nature is 'preservation or exploitation' in the humans' interest. See Maarif 2018, 109-110.

³⁶ Environmentalists widely criticise this section in light of the ecological crisis, including those who see the influence of anthropocentrism on nature. Cf. White 1967; Simkins 2014; Zeidan 2002; Hoffman and Sandelands 2005.

³⁷ David Zeidan shows that not only Christian theology, but the theology of dominant religions as well influences the construction of religious concepts prevalent in the world today. Cf. Zeidan 2002, 207-228.

³⁸ Cf. Maarif 2018, 110; Fitzgerald 2007, 4; Picard 2011, 2.

110), to the exclusion of the importance of other elements. He agrees that early Christian theologians uprooted religion (concepts, meanings, and practices) from its ‘indigenous’ perspectives commonly associated with the Roman notion of *religio*.³⁹

In response to this, Maarif introduced the indigenous religion paradigm as an alternative to the world religions paradigm – or at least he hopes it will be included in the study of the religious practices of indigenous peoples. His example of the forest can help in mapping out the differences between the world religions paradigm and the indigenous religion paradigm. In the world religions paradigm, the concept of ‘spirit’ in the forest is often associated with a person who goes into the forest to perform certain religious practices (referring to Edward B. Taylor’s animist ideas). Maarif explains that in this concept the forest is viewed only as a living place for the spirit, and without the ‘spirit’, the forest is not a substantial entity on its own. Religious practices carried out in the forest are intended to accommodate the encounter of the individual who comes to the forest with the spirit in the forest. In the indigenous religion paradigm, the practice of visiting the forest is understood as recontextualising the intersubjective/personal relationship (between the human person and the forest itself) in a religious way. In summary, for Maarif, the cosmological domains in the indigenous religion paradigm are occupied by human and non-human beings in ‘subject-subject’ or ‘inter-subjective’ relational patterns. The paradigm and hierarchy of the three realms of the world religions does not apply to the indigenous religious paradigm. Maarif writes, ‘[B]ecause the subject or person is not limited to but extended beyond humans, non-human beings can also do ‘culturing’ (Maarif 2018, 115), or, in other words, non-humans beings can also have ‘civilisation’. Their contributions (the influence of the subject/person/entities) are seen

³⁹ For the Romans, *religio* concerns *traditio*. In a sense, *religio* is associated with a set of ancestral practices developed by people and transmitted generationally. Cf. Maarif 2018, 110 and Picard 2011, 1. Sachot called this Roman notion of *religio* a Roman pagan framework (Sachot 2007, 1 and Picard 2011, 1). According to Asmann (2003, 4), the term ‘pagan’ was deliberately coined by secondary religious groups, including Christians, to show the differences in type and degree between their group and the primary religion (which was associated with idolatry and superstition).

as the ‘personhood’⁴⁰ (personality) of entities, so they are potential persons, just like humans.⁴¹

Here, Maarif states that he also adopts Nurit Bird David’s thoughts on ‘relational personhood’ when the latter speaks of the Nayaka in India and their ecological perception of the environment. Bird-Davis states that indigenous people like the Nayaka extend the idea of personhood to non-human beings (Maarif 2015, 151; Bird-David 1999, 69-81). In various field activities related to indigenous peoples in Indonesia, Maarif sees the same tendency when it comes to personhood. He even arrived at three primary principles for establishing relationships in the shared cosmology. Since relationships must be woven and built on a daily basis between oneself and others, three keys are required: responsibility, ethics, and reciprocity.⁴² It is clear that the shared cosmology contradicts the hierarchical cosmology.

We may conclude that, in the indigenous religion paradigm, religion is intended to embrace the cosmos, whereas the world religions paradigm polarises the cosmos. In the context of the historical background described in the previous section, the conception of religion, which was finally set by the Dutch colonial policy, was intended to clarify identity and facilitate the codification of distinctions when applied within the community.⁴³ Unfortunately, the concept of the ‘indigenous religion paradigm’ as practised by the indigenous peoples in Indonesia is considered

⁴⁰ Maarif chose the word ‘personhood’ in connection with the idea of ‘person’. For him, this term conveys the sense of an ability to respond. Person here refers to a ‘being’ – both ‘human and non-human (visible or invisible). Thus, for the world religions paradigm, the forest cannot become a ‘person’ because the forest cannot respond. Moreover, for Western and modern people, the personhood is identical with human beings (Maarif 2018, 114). But in the indigenous religious paradigm, the contribution of the forest (a response) to humans is also the personality of the forest itself, for example, the giver of life, the protector of nature, and so on. The examples mentioned are its response to humans as well as the personhood (personality) of the forest as a being. In several seminars presented by Maarif, we also hear that not only forests but also stones, wood, glass, plates, and so on are considered ‘persons’ in the context of the indigenous religious paradigm because they display personality based on the contributions they make. So, the forest has the potential to become human. Given this, we can understand Maarif’s explanation that the arrival of a person in the forest in the context of religious practice is not based on any reason for the existence of spirits in the forest but is a way to recontextualise inter-subjective/personal relationships between humans and the forest. See Maarif 2018, 113-119.

⁴¹ For example, the sun can provide light to illuminate the world after the night has passed. In this case, the personhood of the sun is the light in darkness. Because the sun has a personality, it has the potential to be the same as humans.

⁴² Cf. Maarif 2018, 119; 2021, 460.

⁴³ This would be one of the seeds of identity politics that divides Indonesia the most to date.

incompatible with the European (now called the Western) modernisation project. If we return to Snouck Hurgronje's thinking, then the practice of indigenous peoples is related to what is called superstition (Snouck Hurgronje 1985, 320). The indigenous people's religious practices, known for their orthopraxis, could be called nothing more than 'mere tradition'⁴⁴ and had to submit to the power of orthodoxy, which is called 'true religion'.⁴⁵

Religion, Non-Religion and/or Belief: Divisions in the Context of Indonesia before Independence

Based on the descriptions above, it will not be difficult to predict that the seeds of a more significant division that were planted between groups were categorised above as 'true religion' and 'mere tradition'.⁴⁶ Clifford Geertz distinguishes these two groups by the names Islam Santri (puristic Islam emphasising the international and universalistic teachings of Mohammed⁴⁷) and (Islam) Abangan (1996, 121-130). Geertz adds that the Abangan group was connected with secular nationalism and Marxism⁴⁸ that developed among the civil servants and the expanding proletariat in cities. This Abangan group reinforced pre-Islamic elements, namely indigenous religious practice and Hindu teachings that already existed in the area, so that the results of their combination can balance the strength of Islamic puristic groups (Geertz 1993, 149).

After Snouck Hurgronje's advice and the Dutch colonial policy on religion recognised Islam, the movement towards modern Islam became more intense. Disputes between puristic Islamic groups (Santri) and Abangan groups became increasingly common. When the Dutch finally left Indonesia and were replaced by the Japanese, the conflict escalated in the period prior to Indonesian independence.

⁴⁴ The phrase 'mere traditions' referred to here concerns two different groups. The first group is entirely separate from the religious group called 'true religion' and adhere completely to indigenous religions. The second concerns groups that practise Islamic teachings and pre-Islamic religious practices simultaneously.

⁴⁵ Cf. Picard 2011, 2.

⁴⁶ 'Mere traditions' here refers to those who combine Islamic and pre-Islamic practices.

⁴⁷ The international and universalistic teachings of Muhammad refer to doctrines and practices that are not influenced by local interpretations or conceptions. Local interpretation is viewed as reducing the value of universally applicable Islamic teachings. See Geertz 1996, 149.

⁴⁸ On that basis, when conflict occurred after Indonesia's independence, the Abangan community was associated with 'communist' groups and had to be crushed. The other alternative was to convert to a religion recognised by the government at that time.

Given the persistent desire on the part of the puristic group (Santri) to form an Islamic state, there have been several differences of opinion between the Santri and Abangan groups regarding the basis of the state they want to form. One of the issues raised here is the separation between religion and *kepercayaan* (literally ‘belief’). This issue is related to the seven words that were rejected before the Indonesian government issued and announced the Preamble to the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.⁴⁹ The Abangan group and non-Muslim groups expressed their refusal to be affiliated with an independent Indonesian state if the seven words were still included in the Constitution. The seven words that would have been included are as follows:

[T]herefore the independence of Indonesia is formulated in a constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which is built into a sovereign state based on a belief in God ‘with the obligation for the adherents of Islam to carry out Islamic law’ [*dengan kewajiban menjalankan Syari’at Islam bagi pemeluk-pemeluknya*- ‘seven words’], a just and civilized humanity, the unity of Indonesia, and democratic life led by wisdom of thoughts in deliberation amongst representatives of the people, and achieving social justice for all the people of Indonesia (Boland 2013, 23-6; Picard 2011, 12).

The founding fathers of Indonesia agreed to eliminate the seven words on the grounds of equality for all religious people. This refusal caused discontent among the Islamic Santri, but they could still claim a victory. They had succeeded in including the words ‘religion and belief’ in Article 29 (2) of the 1945 Constitution. Their goal in this article was to show their identity and differences from the Abangan group. Having no other choice, the Abangan group, which right from the start wanted to separate religion and politics, was forced to propose the term ‘belief’ to refer to their religious practice in order to remain included in the provisions of the Constitution. It would be even more dangerous if they had not included the term ‘belief’. In the end, Article 29 (2) reads: ‘The state guarantees all person’s freedom of worship, each according to his/her own religion or belief’.⁵⁰

⁴⁹ This is actually a continuation of the Jakarta Charter that was composed in June of that same year.

⁵⁰ See <http://luk.tsipil.ugm.ac.id/atur/UUD1945.pdf> (accessed 20 March 2022): The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia as amended by the First Amendment of 1999, the Second Amendment of 2000, the Third Amendment of 2001, and the Fourth Amendment of 2002, <https://jdih.bapeten.go.id/unggah/dokumen/peraturan/116-full.pdf> (accessed 20 March 2022). In this amendment, Article 29 (2) still has the same sentence structure in which it was first issued.

The Abangan group finally accepted the term ‘belief’ because they did not want to be included under the term ‘religion’ (as one of the major religions in the world). In relation to this, Maarif said that this group had predicted that Islamic Santri would use this point to oppress them (2018, 19-21). This victory in Article 29 eventually became the basis for the constitutional distinction between ‘religion’ and ‘belief’ in the new state of Indonesia in 1945. Various cases resulting from neglect, discrimination, and criminalisation due to the distinction between ‘religion’ and ‘belief’ to date can provide justification for the Abangan group’s predictions. I assume that when religion is placed as an identity marker (as it has been since the time of Snouck Hurgronje) that leads to differentiation, the impact is very damaging in the Indonesian context.⁵¹

Unfortunately, the Islamic Santri’s desire did not stop there because they submitted another request the day after the Indonesian government issued the Preamble and the 1945 Constitution. The request was the establishment of a Ministry of Religion⁵² to accommodate the aspirations of the Muslim majority group, which was finally inaugurated on 3 January 1946 (Maarif 2018, 22). The ministry, which was legalised and institutionalised, had also begun to issue various policies that have further widened the gap between religion and belief.⁵³ The dichotomy of religion is becoming stronger, with the assumption that religions recognised by the government tend to be the most appropriate for Indonesia.⁵⁴ Gradually,

⁵¹ Jane Monnig Atkinsons even said, ‘[R]eligious policy in Indonesia is not a unification strategy, but a divisive instrument’. She stated firmly that indigenous religious groups were even viewed as failing to meet the aspirations of progressive Indonesian citizens (Atkinson 1983, 689). If religion is born and develops in conjunction with the motivation to build identity, it contains the potential for division within it. There is no denying that, in some situations, identity has its benefits (cf. Layder 2004; Castells 2010). But if religion was introduced to build identity, as was done through religious policy in the Dutch East Indies following Snouck Hurgronje’s advice and continued after Indonesian independence, the religious divisions seen in Indonesia today are a clear result. This situation is very different from one of the Indonesian religious groups on Sumatra Island: the Orang Rimba. The latter do not even give a name (identity) for their religious beliefs and practices but continue to practise it right up to the present.

⁵² Now we call it the MoRA (Ministry of Religious Affairs) in Indonesia.

⁵³ Even though the Ministry of Religion is now trying to represent all religions, historical facts still show that the reasons for the formation of this ministry and its initial policies clearly represent the interests of Muslims as the majority. Evidence that the Ministry of Religion has not escaped its history is that it does not have a department for indigenous religious communities. Until recently, the regulation of indigenous religious communities was placed under the Ministry of Education and Culture (not considered part of religion).

⁵⁴ The term ‘appropriate’ in this sentence is similar to the understanding of ‘true religions’ on page 15 above, and not much different from the Western standards set by

after gaining independence, the term ‘belief’ was rarely heard and was replaced by the term ‘non-religion’ in the general public.⁵⁵ They were also

the colonial power. But the concept of true religion which is called ‘appropriate’ in this context, is related more to the political situation at the beginning of Indonesia’s independence period. In this case, the recognition of religion cannot be separated from the political map of Indonesia at that time. A long explanation of this can be found in Maarif’s work on religious recognition in Indonesia (2018).

⁵⁵ This situation arises from a decree enacted by Sukarno (the first Indonesian president), which was subsequently implemented by Suharto (the second president): Presidential Decree No. 1/PNPS/1965 on the Prevention of Blasphemy and Abuse of Religions (PNPS 1965, 1-7). This decree shows the recognition of six religions in Indonesia (Islam, Protestantism, Catholicism, Hinduism, Buddhism, and Confucianism) and prohibits any ‘deviant interpretation’ from teachings related to those religions. The state thus safeguards the six religions and prohibits any activity in the name of ‘religious activities’ or with religious characteristics outside these six recognised religions. An example of a prohibited activity is calling a belief a religion and then practising it (see the explanation of PNPS 1965 Article 1). The decree stated previously that the ‘perpetrators’ or their communities would be issued a warning. But if they continued to disobey it, they would be threatened with a sentence of five years (see PNPS 1965 Article 3). In fact, when they were linked to members of the communist party in 1965, they were also sentenced to death (Putra et al. 2019, 493). At the same time, the alleged coup (which has not yet been proven) attributed to the Indonesian Communist Party (PKI) through the G30SPKI incident in 1965 made the situation even more difficult. Eka Putra and his co-authors stated that, in 1965, the PKI was blamed for the death of six TNI officials after being tortured. They revealed that the stories that emerged in the community described the Indonesian Communist Party as a group of atheists, traitors, evil, etc. This situation further legitimised discrimination and violence against PKI members. Many victims were executed or imprisoned without trial (Putra et al. 2019, 493). In this situation, adherents of indigenous religious groups that were already classified as ‘beliefs’ during the period of independence, which in the general public understanding became ‘non-religious’, were equated with ‘atheists’ and finally with ‘communists’. Thus, the presence of the 1965 PNPS and the post-independence political struggle put pressure on indigenous religious groups. But I believe that the central issue of religion in Indonesia, in which indigenous religious groups were ultimately oppressed, did not originate from the 1965 PNPS. This decree only clarifies the main issues behind it. The basis of my argument is the explanation of Article 1 of the 1965 PNPS, which states that ‘the government is trying to direct ... to a healthy view’ groups that have ‘deviant interpretations’ of these religions. This concept is the same as the model applied by Snouck Hurgronje when he stated that local traditions (including religious beliefs and practices) can still be led in the direction of modernisation (a healthy direction; a healthy view as endorsed by the Dutch colonial government). I think that the 1965 PNPS is a form of neo-colonialism. In line with Mignolo’s notion that the dark side of modernity to date is ‘continuous colonial reproduction’ (2007, 450), I hold that there is no modernism without colonialism (cf. Quijano 2000, 548). The Indonesian government, policies, and society are still working with Eurocentric (Western) efforts in religious matters, despite flying the flag of independence. Mignolo illustrates that we are still bound to the ‘spell of the rhetoric of modernity’ from its imperial imaginary articulated in the rhetoric of democracy (Mignolo 2011, 48; Kaunda and Hewitt 2015, 378).

viewed as ‘communists’. It is only recently that the terms ‘belief’ and ‘indigenous religion’ have been heard and even championed. The debate on this continues, though no longer between the Santri and the Abangan but between adherents of the world religion paradigm and those of the indigenous religion paradigm. As long as there is no review of past political tensions, the idea of ‘religion and belief’ will continue to be formulated on that same basis. Moreover, the extension of time (for neglect, humiliation and discrimination) will continue to apply to the victims of this idea – the indigenous peoples.

ANOTHER APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING RELIGION IN INDONESIA

Lessons from the History of the Concept of Religion in Indonesia

To arrive at my approach, I will start by summarising the historical essence of the concept of religion in Indonesia. There are several points that can be understood from the history of this concept in Indonesia.

- (1) The history of the concept of religion in Indonesia proves that, if religion is appropriated for identity needs (including for the purpose of differentiation or coding as a sign of difference), the impact will be very detrimental. In fact, the indigenous religion in Indonesia actually embraces the entity – embraces the cosmos – (the approach of the indigenous religion paradigm) and does not divide or build a hierarchy (the approach of the world religions paradigm).
- (2) The history of the concept of religion in Indonesia proves that ‘religion is a source for an unbalanced living system in society’ (cf. the position of religion and custom – which we will map as ‘belief and/or non-religion’ following Snouck Hurgronje’s advice).
- (3) The history of the concept of religion in Indonesia proves that religion is the best basis for a *divide and conquer* policy in Indonesia and Indonesia’s ‘Achilles heel’ (cf. the situation in Aceh⁵⁶ during the colonial period⁵⁷).
- (4) The history of the concept of religion in Indonesia proves that the concept that has been in effect since the colonial period was attacked for

⁵⁶ I am not saying that Snouck Hurgronje intended to carry out a divide and conquer policy in Aceh. Instead, he looked for the easiest way out. Nevertheless, he did not realise that the community itself ends up weakened and easily defeated because of the internal conflicts.

⁵⁷ At that time, the Dutch government faced difficulties in conquering Aceh. In this situation, religion became the access point that indirectly divided the Acehnese and made it easier for the Dutch to control the area. See pages 6-11 above.

reasons of economic interest (capitalism) and from the perspective of modernism, which remains unchanged.

(5) The history of the concept of religion in Indonesia shows that, although the Islamic Santri community tried to realise a ‘state based on religion’ after independence, the decisive characteristic of the prevailing religion in Indonesia today is not Islam-Indonesia or Indigenous religion-Indonesia, but Westernised Indonesia⁵⁸.

The Congruent Approach

The general religious concept in Indonesia came from contexts outside Indonesia and was then made a part of Indonesia and even became the basis for perceiving religious issues in Indonesia. In light of that, I offer a congruent approach. This approach is not intended to fall into the trap of forming a specific and ‘universally applicable’ religious meaning as in Fitzgerald (2007,4). It is actually intended as an approach to understanding religion that is, in fact, very dynamic.

Understanding the congruent approach must begin with a basic understanding of the term congruent. In the *Oxford Learner’s Dictionary* (2015), ‘congruent’ is defined as an adjective in two ways. First, in the context of geometry, it refers to things being of the same size and shape. Second, to be congruent (with something) (in a formal sense) is to be suitable for something, appropriate in a particular situation. In the first meaning, the elements that are brought together must be the same in the geometrical context. If the term congruent (with something) is used in connection with society, it must be realised that the geometric mathematical pattern cannot fully measure a dynamic society in an adequate way. The emphasis is not on being the same but on being suitable for something or appropriate in a given situation.

Let us take humans as an example. No one human is exactly the same as another; even twins have some genetic elements that differentiate them. At one point, different human beings come together in a situation in order to find a suitable point between them, a point that is appropriate in that particular situation. The emphasis is not on differences but on the ‘suitable’ and ‘appropriate’ points in that particular situation. To attain the level of congruence, each side must compromise in order to at least approach the point of congruence. These points will prove more challenging to reach if this is not done. Another possibility is that certain parties will pay a higher price than others (who do not have to pay any price perhaps) but those who bear the costs will continue to do so to keep the process ‘congruent’.

⁵⁸ See page 15 above.

With the Indonesian background in mind, I will now present a congruent approach to understanding religion.

(1) The starting point for the conceptualisation of religion is not awareness of differences (identity, point of view, and others) but the awareness of and intention to find the best common ground (meeting point/point of congruence) that can be achieved together, supported by the awareness these are interdependent entities. This follows the principle of indigenous Indonesian religious thought, which embraces the cosmos and does not construct different identities that create cosmic barriers.

(2) Every entity involved in determining the understanding of religion must be viewed as a subject, with a subject-subject or intersubjectivity relationship pattern.

(3) Because relations are dynamic processes according to the context of meetings between entities, the concept of religion that is formed is fluid but still related to the context of its meaning. In the middle of the parliamentary chamber for decision making regarding the meaning of religion, each entity involved must guarantee that the meaning formed follows 'the shared context' at that time. One of the parliamentarians decides to walk into the forest after the meeting and contemplates the meaning of religion when he relates to the trees. In that case, the concept of religion that is born must represent the entity he encounters. Therefore, the congruent approach provides space for 'individuals' and 'communities' to be open to constantly reviewing (rereading/retracing)⁵⁹ their understanding of religion in different places, times and situations.

(4) The process towards becoming congruent must ensure the representation of all entities involved in reconceptualising the meaning of religion, even though these entities may not be physically present. By way of illustration, in the indigenous religion paradigm, when a person comes into contact with a candle, wood, and plate (which do not speak), or even air or wind (which is formless), then the contribution of these elements is

⁵⁹ It is interesting to see this since Cicero understands tradition in the sense of *relegere* i.e., 'retrace', 'reread', which greatly respects the context in which the religious tradition lives (cf. Cicero 1961, 193; Hoyt 1912, 127). Unfortunately, this idea of religion was replaced by Lactantius' view. The latter was a Christian theologian who linked the term *relegare* (to bind)' to a very 'iconophobic and anti-material' Christian content (Houtman and Meyer 2012, 11). Sachot even stated that Lactantius had 'uprooted this term from its pagan framework' (Sachot 2007, 1). Asmann also criticised the use of the term 'pagan' as deliberately coined by secondary religious groups, including Christians, to distinguish themselves from the prevailing religion, which was then associated with what is considered idolatry and superstition (2003, 4). Unfortunately, Lactantius' view has remained influential to this day. Given the context of ancient Roman thought, Cicero's view is in line with the indigenous people's view of their religious traditions.

considered to be evidence of the ‘personality’ of the element. With that personality, wind, water, rock, soil, and even people or communities that are not present must be treated in an intersubjective pattern and awareness of interdependence. Maarif’s three essential principles need to be promoted here, namely, the responsible, ethical, and reciprocal principles that must be prioritised in the relations between entities when making decisions, even though there are entities that cannot attend in person. This point is vital because many minority groups cannot be involved (due to limited funds, distance, etc.) in determining the concept of religion. But their absence must still be understood as another ‘subject’ in the pattern of intersubjectivity during the decision making.

(5) In determining the concept of religion, the congruence of the background perspective with the context of the local situation must be ensured.

Conclusion

Conflict in various aspects of life related to religion and belief in Indonesia is a type of butterfly effect from situations in the past. Economic reasons and the perspective of modernism that were deliberately embedded in political policy were the main factors behind religious policy in the Dutch East Indies. Without explaining this background, the government could do little more than continue to build on the foundations that had been laid by the previous Dutch government. The main characteristic that emerges from the concept and policy of religion in Indonesia is not Indonesian Islam or indigenous Indonesian religion, but the characteristics of Westernised Indonesia. The congruent approach should be taken into consideration when reviewing the understanding of religion in Indonesia. The hope behind this approach is that the concept of religion that later emerged bears the characteristics of Indonesian religion.

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